

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Literature review and conceptual framework on mechanisms of how biomass trade affects biodiversity as input to D3.2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

International trade of agricultural exports has recently been linked to almost half of global biodiversity losses. Trade flow analyses indicate that an increasing share of products consumed in the global north is produced in the global south, where biodiversity is the highest, and where the livelihoods of many local communities depend on nature. To address this issue, trade-related environmental policies and governance mechanisms are currently being designed and implemented; however, whether these may effectively mitigate biodiversity decline remains uncertain. One reason is that metrics to measure biodiversity impact are still in their infancy, and thus there are uncertainties about their accuracy and comparability across regions and over time. Another important reason is that there are cross-disciplinary gaps in our theoretical and empirical understanding of the mechanisms through which trade affects biodiversity.

To shed light on these research gaps across scientific fields, we reviewed recent scientific literature linking agricultural trade and biodiversity, and identified different thematic areas that aim to explain potential trade-driven impacts on biodiversity. We cover the following themes:

- a) Environmental impacts of trade liberalization
- b) Comparative advantage and the potential of land sparing
- c) Highly heterogeneous effects across crops and regions
- d) Governance solutions for future sustainability

Taking the drivers and mechanisms identified in the literature into consideration, in the second half of this report we propose a conceptual framework for subsequent CLEVER work, “Addressing trade-driven biodiversity impacts”. Here, we provide a non-exhaustive overview of currently available biodiversity metrics (alongside limitations and considerations), and relate the hypotheses identified in section 1 to conditions that determine the potential leverage of different policies and governance mechanisms.

We conclude by highlighting remaining research gaps, relevant hypotheses to be tested, and recommend pathways forward towards designing and evaluating cross-sectoral agri-environmental policies that have an impact on biodiversity outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity is in global decline and agricultural trade has been identified as a major underlying driver of this loss. Due to changes in land-use destined for exports, as well as the direct exploitation of resources, increases in international trade and consumption have been linked to 50% of global biodiversity loss, 30% of threats on animal species, and 25% of projected global extinctions (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019; Díaz & Malhi, 2022; Lenzen et al., 2012). At the same time, these threats to biodiversity are most acute where biodiversity is richest – in tropical hotspots across the global south, such as Brazil, Indonesia, and Central Africa.

While there is consensus that biodiversity is in decline, and that agricultural trade is a key driver of this loss (Pendrill et al., 2019, 2022), finding and leveraging solutions for these negative impacts is a challenge. This is in part due to biodiversity data limitations, which have historically depicted an incomplete and biased picture of global biodiversity (Jung, 2023; Oliveira et al., 2016). These limitations mean that, to date, metrics and indices for reporting the global state of biodiversity data are still in their infancy, and as such, methods, metrics, and baselines for describing patterns of biodiversity change are still subject to scientific debate (Bracy Knight et al., 2020; Buschke et al., 2021; Costelloe et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2023; Marshall et al., 2020; Simpson et al., 2022; Valdez et al., 2023). Thus, despite the recent and rapid increase in availability of global biodiversity indicators (e.g., the Living Planet Index (LPI) (Collen et al., 2009), Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII) and the PREDICTS database (Phillips et al., 2021), the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT) and the STAR metric (Mair et al., 2021)), there is still uncertainty about the applicability of these metrics in answering scientific questions regarding the impacts of different drivers on global biodiversity patterns.

Another reason why finding and leveraging solutions for trade-driven biodiversity impacts is challenging is because there are still theoretical and empirical gaps in our understanding on the specific mechanisms through which trade can impact biodiversity. On the one hand, according to economic theory, trade is expected to have an overall neutral (or even positive impact) on overall socio-ecological outcomes because any negative externalities such as pollution – or, the conversion of natural ecosystems to croplands – are outweighed by gains in efficiency of the overall agricultural system of production. That is, mechanisms related to comparative advantage or technological innovation are expected to neutralize or compensate for any negative impacts (Baylis et al., 2021; Cherniwchan et al., 2017; Esty, 2001) (see sections 1.1-2). On the other hand, environmental and ecological research expects globalization and liberalization of trade alongside with increasing consumption patterns to have negative impacts on environmental outcomes because these lead to agricultural expansion in threatened ecosystems (Baylis et al., 2021; Esty, 2001; Kastner, 2021; Ortiz et al., 2021). Evidently, there are gaps in theory and empirical evidence across fields. This includes a better understanding of the specific mechanisms driving positive, negative, or neutral

impacts on biodiversity, and whether there is causally-rigorous empirical evidence to link these.

In parallel, there have been several recent policy efforts aimed towards addressing the trade-biodiversity challenge. For instance, recently adopted European Union due-diligence regulations aim to decrease contributions to deforestation by requiring imports from specific deforestation-risk products to prove their supply chains are free of deforestation, or they would be subject to sanctions, fines, or lawsuits (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Parliament, 2023). Yet, environmental policies may not fully consider implications of these regulations alongside existing trade agreements; for instance, the 2019 EU-Mercosur agreement may contradict environmental commitments also made in the European Green Deal or in the newest Global Biodiversity Framework (Kehoe et al., 2020). Moreover, environmental policies may also have unintended socioeconomic consequences, particularly if there are no mechanisms safeguarding smallholder producers from solely bearing the burden of compliance (Reis et al., 2021). Therefore, without cross-sectoral holistic approaches, current efforts to curb trade-driven impacts on biodiversity may ultimately have little-to-no impact in mitigating biodiversity decline.

Hence, there is an urgent need for 1) better understanding the mechanisms driving trade-related biodiversity impacts 2) designing mechanism-relevant policies and interventions for mitigating trade-driven biodiversity impacts, while also a) ensuring that these assessments and monitoring efforts use meaningful biodiversity metrics, and b) social and ecological outcomes and potential trade-offs alike are rigorously evaluated.

OBJECTIVES

As we aim to better understand the agricultural-trade driven impacts on biodiversity, in this report we aim to:

- Provide a **cross-disciplinary overview on the recent literature linking trade to biodiversity**. This includes organizing the literature into themes in order to organize different aspects of future CLEVER work as well as identifying empirical gaps to be addressed by this future work
- Improve the **conceptual understanding of the specific, potential mechanisms** linking agricultural trade and biodiversity impacts.
- Provide an **overview of biodiversity metrics** currently available to identify potential limitations and opportunities. This should serve as a first guide for CLEVER partners to both use and produce biodiversity-relevant variables and indices in their work.
- Propose a **conceptual framework** for future work evaluating trade impacts on biodiversity.

METHODS

In order to synthesize current understanding on the impacts of agricultural trade on biodiversity, we followed a semi-systematic protocol for identifying and reviewing the literature. We complemented an existing reference list (from the CLEVER project proposal) with a search on Web of Science using the following search terms ("international trade" OR "domestic trade" OR commercialization) AND "environmental outcomes" OR biodiversity OR nature AND effect OR impact), for the period of 2010-2023. We further refined this search by choosing literature that fell within the following Web of Science categories: Environmental Sciences Ecology, Business Economics, Science Technology Other Topics, Biodiversity Conservation, Agriculture, Geography, Forestry, Social Sciences Other Topics, and Development Studies. This search yielded 524 records which were manually screened for relevance, and records that did not cover either trade nor biodiversity were eliminated (alongside less relevant records, such as literature on the topic of wildlife trade or trade impacts on invasive species, as these do not fall within the specific scope of the project). To supplement this main literature search, we also reviewed gray literature in order to gain a better understanding of current agri-environmental trade policies and their planned use of methods and metrics for monitoring biodiversity impact.

Thus, using the existing reference list and newly identified sources, we summarized and assessed information by recording titles, methods, and findings for all relevant papers or reports. Next, for studies or reports that were considered to be highly-relevant, and in particular for existing reviews on the topic, we identified different hypotheses and mechanisms in the text aiming to explain the impacts of trade on biodiversity from different disciplinary perspectives. We also noted any research or policy gaps already identified in this literature. Finally, we categorized these hypotheses, mechanisms, and gaps into themes to inform the narrative-style review presented in the following section of Results and Discussion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Improving our trade-biodiversity understanding: four thematic areas of agricultural trade-driven impacts on biodiversity

1.1 Environmental impacts of trade liberalization

In economics, analyzing the impacts of trade – the exchange of goods – has often had the connotation of trade liberalization, the removal of any barriers to open trade and exchange goods between parties. In the past few decades, the liberalization of agricultural trade has been well established as an integral part of global food systems, having improved the overall wellbeing of many people around the world (Baylis et al., 2021; Winters & Martuscelli, 2014; Xu et al., 2020). At the same time, this liberalization is expected to impact the environment and the use and management of natural resources in different ways. In economics, these mechanisms have often been categorized as *scale*, *composition*, and *technique* effects (Cherniwchan et al., 2017). That is, trade can impact the amount of goods actually produced and consumed (scale), it can change what is produced (composition), where and how agricultural commodities are produced (technique) – i.e., the amounts of (natural) resources needed to produce these, as well as production processes, their configurations, and their required inputs (often through transfer of technologies). Moreover, trade is also expected to change consumption patterns, which can impact demand and subsequently also impact environmental policies (Baylis et al., 2021; Cherniwchan et al., 2017).

However, these environmental impacts have not necessarily been expected to be negative – mechanisms that have positive environmental impacts have typically been expected to neutralize or outweigh any negative externalities. For instance, the “pollution reduction by rationalization” hypothesis posits that trade liberalization has overall neutral or negative environmental impacts because the reorganization of market shares into more efficient configurations will make up for any negative environmental impacts created from the increase in production of goods (Cherniwchan et al., 2017). Trade liberalization is also expected to reorganize the geographic locations where goods are produced due to comparative advantage (see also section 1.2), and thus have overall positive impacts on the environment because production will occur in where it would be most resource-efficient (see top section, **Figure 1**). Therefore, free trade is expected to foster sustainable agricultural production, albeit some argue this requires labeling of sustainably-made products, by for instance, certifying their sustainability through some standard (Moon, 2011; Tscharrntke et al., 2021).

Nonetheless, there are hypotheses in economics that do expect overall negative environmental impacts from trade liberalization (see bottom section, **Figure 1**). Firstly, market failures such as poorly defined property rights can prevent gains in efficiency that would have predicted net-positive environmental effects (Baylis et al., 2021; Bulte

& Barbier, 2005). The “distressed and dirty industry hypothesis” would also expect trade liberalization to have a negative impact on the environment; as it is possible that firms downsize as a result of trade’s reorganization of production processes, and that in this “distress”, some firms will decrease any existing measures in place for mitigating environmental impacts, thus becoming “dirtier” during this transition (Cherniwchan et al., 2017; Forslid et al., 2018). Also, as trade liberalization increases economic incentives towards splitting up and fragmenting the production processes, the dirtiest parts of this production process are also likely to be moved to locations where environmental policies are least strict, thus expecting this fragmentation to increase negative impacts on the environment, the “pollution offshoring hypothesis” (Cherniwchan et al., 2017). This pollution offshoring may easily allow negative environmental effects to go undetected because a production process in a location may suddenly become “cleaner”, yet the dirtiest parts of production have simply been offshored to a new (unmonitored) location, pointing to leakage aspects to consider (Meyfroidt et al., 2020). Relatedly, export status has also been widely considered indicative of a firm’s impact on the environment, with exporting firms typically expected to have lower impacts. However, empirical evidence for the specific mechanisms driving this effect have been elusive thus far. That is, export status could have low impacts because of pollution offshoring, but also simply because of productivity or market effects (Cherniwchan et al., 2017; Forslid et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Summary of the main mechanisms through which trade liberalization can have positive, neutral, or negative effects on biodiversity. First, trade liberalization is expected to impact the environment through scale, composition and technique effects, which are expected to reorganize the market and increase efficiencies in such a way that impacts on natural resources used (and thus on biodiversity) should be positive or neutral. However, these gains in efficiencies may be prevented by existing market failures (such as unclear property rights). Moreover, this market reorganization may also result in the “distressed and dirty” industry hypothesis, or in pollution offshoring, which can have negative impacts on biodiversity.

By contrast, recent research in environmental-sciences has found increasing evidence that global trade is a main global driver of the loss of natural ecosystems and diversity of species. In these studies, trade is often conceptualized more broadly – it is used to refer not only to the opening or increasing of trade relations, but also globalization, local-global links and effects, as well as general impacts of increases in per-capita affluence and consumption, particularly in the global north (Bruckner et al., 2015). Importantly, the main mechanism identified in this line of research is the influence of trade on the location of production and thereby changes in land-use (LU/LUC). Therefore, trade is typically linked to negative environmental outcomes, primarily because it is expected to increase agricultural expansion into natural ecosystems, typically in locations with high biodiversity value (Abman & Lundberg, 2020; Faria & Almeida, 2016; Kastner, 2021). Trade liberalization is considered to increase pressure on forests or natural ecosystems, particularly under conditions where agricultural exports increase deforestation (Bulte & Barbier, 2005; Kastner, 2021). It is also expected to increase the supply of agricultural goods at a global level (scale effects), which in turn increases demand for cropland, shifting the supply of agricultural goods and leading to changes in local land-uses that increase greenhouse gas emissions and impact biodiversity (technique effects) (Hertel et al., 2019; Schmitz et al., 2012).

Across disciplines, there are important remaining gaps in understanding trade liberalization effects. Firstly, as seen from this overview across disciplines, it is evident that quantifying the *net* effects of trade liberalization on environmental outcomes remains contested and an empirically steep challenge due to differences across contexts (Kastner, 2021). Gaining consensus on net effects is a challenge, particularly because so many hypothesized mechanisms on trade-driven environmental impacts have not necessarily been developed in reference to land-use or land-systems, but usually rather, industrial pollutants such as green-house gas emissions (Cherniwchan et al., 2017; Esty, 2001). Additionally, regulating environmental impacts via trade agreements has typically only involved monitoring impact on GHG emissions (see further discussion on heterogeneity of location of impact in **1.3**). Thus, there is a need for further developing theoretical understanding of current global environmental problems in a globalized context – and for developing theories while considering multiple aspects of environmental impacts from multiple disciplinary perspectives (e.g. ecosystem services/nature’s contributions to people (NCP), functional biodiversity, genetic diversity, biodiversity intactness, etc.). Finally, the specific mechanisms driving impacts of trade liberalization remain to be empirically and systematically tested across regions and over time (e.g., the role of export status, the role of property rights as a market failure, whether, where, and when fragmentation of production processes lead to leakage elsewhere, i.e., “dirty and distressed” or “pollution offshoring” effects).

1.2 Comparative advantage and the potential of land sparing

As mentioned in the previous section, one of the main mechanisms through which trade can have an environmental impact is by shifting the geographic location of production (one part of the technique effect). The Heckscher-Ohlin theorem expects that with trade liberalization, countries will export goods that they can produce cheaply due to their abundance, while importing goods that are scarce. Therefore, any gains in the efficient fulfillment of demand for goods is expected to be beneficial for both social and ecological outcomes (Baylis et al., 2021; Bulte & Barbier, 2005). In the case of agricultural trade, this implies an increase in intensive and extensive farming where resources are most abundant and where commodities are cheaper to produce (Baylis et al., 2021). In sum, which locations have a comparative advantage over others plays a key role in determining whether, where, and when trade will have positive or negative environmental impacts (**Figure 2**).

Over the past several years, various studies find evidence for a major global shift in global agricultural production; agricultural goods are increasingly being produced in the global south whereas consumed in the global north – which has associated impacts on natural ecosystems in the location of production (notwithstanding also increasing South-South trade) (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019; Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016; Lenzen et al., 2012; Marques et al., 2019; Pendrill et al., 2019; Plank et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2022a, 2022b; Weinzettel et al., 2013; Wiedmann & Lenzen, 2018). These studies have typically dealt with different aspects of environmental impact, ranging from e.g., quantifying species extinction threats (Lenzen et al., 2012; Marques et al., 2019) to raw material consumption (Plank et al., 2018), or more recently, human impacts on net primary production (NPP) (Roux et al., 2021). They have also used different approaches such as multi-regional input-output (MRIO) analyses (Lenzen et al., 2012; Weinzettel et al., 2013), or physical trade accounting (Kastner, 2021). Although this variety in metrics and approaches might hinder comparability across methodologies and regions, they also indicate a growing evidence base of impacts on different aspects of biodiversity conservation, garnering increasing interest in the issue (Kastner, 2021).

Nonetheless, across different methodological approaches, causally disentangling specific mechanisms of how locations with comparative advantage will determine impacts on biodiversity conservation remains a challenge. For instance, MRIO databases and analyses are considered to be causally rigorous as a quantified impact can be attributed to a source (IEEP et al., 2021), yet they also have limitations related to which products they include in their analyses, and how they link physical trade with monetary data (Schaffartzik et al., 2015). Also, counterfactual scenarios, that is, alternatives to the current model of global food production, remain scarcely used in the literature – and thus the potential transformation of this system is poorly understood.

One such example is the review and analysis by Kastner et al. (2021), where they compare net-trade effects (exports-imports) in 2010 to a no-trade scenario, and find

that if all countries produced what they consumed locally (while assuming same levels of yields), pressure for agricultural expansion would be much higher. This suggests there is currently an overall positive net impact of trade, the agricultural expansion that would take place in a hypothetical scenario where there was no trade is being avoided, and land is being “spared” for nature (Balmford et al., 2005) (albeit there may be regional variations in these net-positive effects (Kastner, 2021)). Yet, while this “no-trade” counterfactual is a useful exercise in aiming to identify net impacts of global trade, it does not help identify potential transformation of this system towards a more sustainable model.

Although not explicitly identified as counterfactual analyses, a couple studies use other interesting points of comparison when estimating effects of trade on different environmental impacts. For instance, Roux et al. go beyond typical land or water “footprint” metrics (e.g., (Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016; Weinzettel et al., 2013)) and use a measure of human-appropriated net primary production (NPP) of ecosystems to try and capture human impacts on ecosystem functioning (Roux et al., 2021). They find that, although the globalization of trade may have had net-positive impacts when comparing impacts in 1999 to 1986, starting from 1999 these impacts started becoming net-negative, with impacts in 2008 being more negative than the trade system in place in 1986. They attribute these impacts to agricultural production shifting to locations where it is *not* most efficient to produce (2021). Marques et al. also use an interesting comparison point by estimating the carbon capture that would occur if global croplands had been allowed to regenerate natural vegetation, and find increasing impacts on carbon sequestration from 2001-2011. While these differences in estimates (e.g., (Kastner, 2021; Roux et al., 2021)) may be due to different methodologies and metrics, they also indicate the importance of investigating net-impacts of trade across temporal scales (see spatial and temporal dependency, **Figure 2**).

Moreover, another important factor to consider in (causally) disentangling specific mechanisms is the role of indirect drivers (such as institutional setups, land markets, and regulations that impact land speculation) in driving agricultural-trade impacts on environmental outcomes. A recent synthesis of pan-tropical deforestation data finds that although agriculture remains an important driver of deforestation, from 2011-2015, only 45-65% of deforested lands were actually used for agricultural production within the next few years (Pendrill et al., 2022). These surprising findings challenge the notion that there is a direct trade-off between agricultural *production* and biodiversity conservation. Instead, they suggest an ongoing “lose-lose” scenario where agricultural production (and associated food security) is *not* increasing while tropical forests and biodiversity are being lost. In sum, better addressing indirect, underlying drivers that impact land-use decision-making remains a priority.

Therefore, despite evidence for comparative advantage reorganizing agricultural production at a global level, and notwithstanding the spatiotemporal and direct/indirect nuances of these effects, evidence indicates that comparative advantage alone fails to explain global environmental impacts of trade. Indeed, there are hypothesized

mechanisms that expect comparative advantage to interact with other factors (**Figure 2**). For instance, the stickiness of trade relations are also expected to have a great deal of influence on bilateral and multilateral trade relations (Reis et al., 2023; Villoria & Hertel, 2011) – which may defy other expectations following the comparative advantage principle that assume rapidly shifting trade-relations under perfectly integrated markets (Hertel et al., 2019). Moreover, traditionally, resource endowments and differences in available technologies have been considered the main determinants of comparative advantage (rather than agri-environmental policies). However, the “pollution haven hypothesis” also argues that comparative advantage can be determined by policies, as reducing barriers to trade could lead to pollution-intensive industries to decrease in countries with strict environmental regulation, and increase in those with weaker regulations. Ultimately, although a location with comparative advantage may have traditionally been defined by the abundance of resources and the ease with which to produce these, it is evident that current global agricultural-trade setups may have failed to incorporate ecological costs into this definition (Roux et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Summary of the main mechanisms through which comparative advantage (the technique effect) can have both positive and negative outcomes on biodiversity. Comparative advantage can increase exports and intensive and extensive farming in locations where resources are abundant and cheaply produced, whereas increase imports of scarce goods in other locations. Positive or negative impacts on biodiversity are spatially and temporally dependent, i.e., effects will depend on which locations have a comparative advantage, when. Other factors such as the stickiness of trade and the stringency of environmental policies can also impact which locations have comparative advantage over others.

To better address these challenges in disentangling comparative advantage effects, potential land sparing, and other underlying drivers of trade-driven impacts, future research could address several remaining gaps. First, causally-rigorous studies could identify and use alternative counterfactuals that are more closely relevant to options for transforming the current global trade system (e.g., exploring the restoration potential of agricultural lands), as well as incorporate evidence from integrated assessment models

(IAMs) (Leclère et al., 2020). Second, it will be important to further investigate where/when comparative advantage has shifted locations of agricultural production to where it is no longer efficient by, for instance, pairing data on ecosystem functioning with trade-flow analyses (e.g. MRIOs). These analyses could also answer whether efficiency gains from comparative advantage have failed to account for ecosystem services that may have been irreversibly lost. Third, further research could investigate the complex interactions of comparative advantage with other factors such as stickiness of trade relations, or policy spillovers, as well as other underlying governance factors.

1.3 Highly heterogeneous effects across agricultural systems and regions

One main finding in the literature on the impacts of trade on the environment and biodiversity is that effects are highly heterogeneous across contexts and across biodiversity measures. Indeed, producing the same crop in different locations can have different impacts on biodiversity conservation (Hoang et al., 2023). Although this heterogeneity can make it difficult to synthesize generalized effects, different theoretical and empirically-based hypotheses for the heterogeneity of effects exist, mainly around 1) crop-types (because of management regimes and price elasticities), and 2) across global regions (due to landscape or biophysical characteristics).

First, effects are expected to be heterogeneous across crop types that are being produced primarily because specific crops can have distinct management requirements (e.g., rotation cycles, fertilizer and/or water requirements) (Baylis et al., 2021; Kastner, 2021). Moreover, the level of intensity with which agriculture is produced is expected to be negatively related to biodiversity indicators, i.e., the “yield hypothesis” expects that as yields increase, biodiversity decreases. However, yield effects are expected to be logarithmic or quadratic because yield increases in places with already-high land-use intensity might only have marginal impacts on biodiversity. Moreover, the yield hypothesis may only affect certain taxa, as high yield crops have been observed to highly impact birds, but not plants or invertebrates (Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2021) (see **Figure 3**). There are also hypotheses within the field of biofuels that expect crop “generation” to impact biodiversity because second-generation crops (i.e., fuels derived from woody-plant crops or their residues) may have attributes that are more similar to natural environments than first-generation crops (fuels derived from oils, sugar, and starchy crops). Similarly, these effects have mostly been observed to impact birds and plants (Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2021).

Effects of different agricultural products are also expected to interact with the area of a land parcel as area is associated with diversity of crops as well as likelihood of export status (Forslid et al., 2018; Kastner, 2021; Noack et al., 2022). For instance, crops produced in relatively smaller areas (e.g., sugarcane, palm oil, rubber, and coffee) can have large impact (Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016) (reason for which many argue that the “land” or area-footprint of trade is not a good measure of impact on biodiversity).

However, these area-effects may be an artifact for land-use intensification or “simplification” (Noack et al., 2022).

Moreover, heterogeneity of effects across crop-types is also expected due to different crop price elasticities. Globally, crops with higher price elasticities are found to have a higher impact on bird diversity and CO₂ emissions, and Marques et al. associate this impact with an increase in consumption of these crops due to economic growth (2019). Additionally, when commodities with high-price elasticity of demand (e.g., rubber, sugarcane, palm oil, soybeans, and tropical fruits) are more intensively produced, these are expected to cause a “rebound” effect, and their production would increase agricultural expansion (Meyfroidt et al., 2020). By contrast, the intensification of staple crops such as wheat and rice are expected to result in land sparing in the long term (Rodríguez García et al., 2020), indicating overall smaller impacts on LUC and associated biodiversity impacts (**Figure 3**).

Second, there has also been ample evidence for the heterogeneity of effects across global regions. For instance, Kastner et al. find that, although there is evidence for avoided biodiversity impacts as a result of the trade from North America to Central America and the Caribbean (due to high endemism in this region), this pattern did not hold at all locations or scales (Kastner, 2021); exports into Europe were found to induce – not avoid – biodiversity impacts. These differences in effects across regions may be due to liberalization and comparative advantage reasons previously discussed (**1.1-2**), but also because these factors are inherently related to the heterogeneity of biophysical conditions across regions. Hence, some more specific landscape-related mechanisms driving these effects include differences in existing ecosystems, i.e., effects will depend on what precise ecosystems are being replaced by agricultural production (Foster et al., 2003; Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2021) (note, this relates to the challenge of defining a baseline level of biodiversity, see discussion in section **2.1**). Here, the general expectation is that biodiversity should be higher in natural ecosystems than croplands, albeit, it is important to note that effects may vary across taxa. For instance, in a recent meta-analysis, bioenergy-specific croplands were found to have a nonsignificant impact on amphibian and reptile abundance, and even increased the number of mammal species (due to the introduction of alien species, e.g., rodents) (Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2021).

Relatedly, the “dissimilar land use hypothesis” posits that converting reference ecosystems to croplands with greater differences in ecological structure should have the highest biodiversity impacts (e.g., primary-forest conversion to grasslands). Finally, the endowment of certain ecosystems such as forests, is also expected to influence different effects across regions, as forest surplus is observed to increase agriculture-export driven deforestation, and vice-versa (Kastner, 2021).

Figure 3. Summary of the main mechanisms via which crop-type, crop-price elasticity, and world regions can have heterogeneous effects on biodiversity. Different crops are managed differently, and at different intensities, which may or may not impact biodiversity negatively, depending on the taxa. Crops with high price elasticities are typically expected to have a negative impact on biodiversity because they are likely to induce agricultural expansion, whereas crops with low price elasticities are expected to have a low impact on biodiversity because their intensification is expected to have a land sparing effect. Finally, biodiversity is affected differently across world regions because the level of impact of land-use conversions will depend on the reference ecosystems being replaced. Here, effects are also expected to vary across taxa.

In conclusion, there are many complex and interacting factors that may determine the high heterogeneity of agriculture-trade driven effects on biodiversity outcomes, underscoring the importance of considering local contexts in disentangling effects. In this regard, it is important for future research to consider how crop diversity and the conversion of specific, existing ecosystems can be leveraged for potential mitigation of biodiversity loss. Furthermore, future research could include empirically testing different land-use transitions and their biodiversity impacts (e.g., differences of effects when converting forest to shrublands, to croplands, etc.). Moreover, while it is important for future research to continue identifying potential inter-regional leakage of effects (e.g., how European due diligence policies can produce soy export leakage to Asian, Russian, or Middle Eastern markets), future research could also further investigate intra-regional differences of effects at finer scales, for instance how soy production has moved from the Amazon biome to nearby Cerrado regions in Brazil or neighboring countries (e.g. (Villoria et al., 2022)). Although intra-regional policy leakage is identified as a key research area, it remains a research frontier given the methodological challenges for empirical testing.

1.4 Governance solutions for future sustainability

Recently, there has been an increasing interest in creating and strengthening governance responses to curb the impacts of agricultural-trade on biodiversity. Yet, we found relatively few hypotheses and specified mechanisms regarding the expected impacts of specific governance response options, often rather focusing on economic tools (e.g., regulating trade via policies or other measures resulting in “dirty and distressed” or “pollution haven” effects), or trade relations (e.g., stickiness). This is likely in part due to observational and methodological challenges of testing for the influence of underlying governance conditions. However, theoretically and empirically evaluating governance response options remains an important research gap.

Nonetheless, we found governance-related hypotheses were very general. For instance, some traditional arguments posit that negative environmental externalities from trade only happen if countries have weak governance, as economic theory generally expects trade to have net-positive impacts on both social and ecological outcomes (Baylis et al., 2021). In another instance, some expect that changing livelihood dependence from subsistence crops to export agriculture (and associated decreases in poverty) will decrease pressure on local forests (Bulte & Barbier, 2005), pointing to unresolved, persistent hypotheses on the socioeconomic drivers of environmental degradation. However, these expectations could also conflict with other hypotheses that expect export agriculture to also lead to increased pressure on forests (see discussions in 1.1,1.3) (**Figure 4Error! Reference source not found.**).

It is also possible that governance levels have a U-shaped effect on biodiversity (**Figure 4Error! Reference source not found.**). In other words, it is possible to relate governance effects to the environmental Kuznets curve (Esty, 2001), where economic growth is expected to increase pollution (i.e., decreasing biodiversity) up until a certain level, and subsequently decrease at higher levels of economic growth. Here, however, drawing from institutional economics hypotheses (Baland & Platteau, 1996; Deacon, 1994), we posit that biodiversity impacts may be highest at medium-governance levels compared to poor/strong governance levels, because minimum governance capacities are required to successfully exploit land-related natural resources, but higher levels of governance would lead to strictly enforced environmental regulation that prevents such exploitation (Cherniwchan et al., 2017).

Aside from the above hypotheses, there are a variety of environmental efforts and policies underway aiming to address and prevent biodiversity impacts of agricultural trade. The recent regulation on deforestation-free supply chains as a part of the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2022) has received much attention for its commitment to banning the import (and export) of deforestation-associated commodities into Europe. This effectively requires the assurance that imports have been produced legally and are “deforestation-free” by 2024, and is using a new benchmarking system for due diligence and inspection obligations that distinguishes between products that originate from areas with low-risk and high-risk of deforestation

(Berning & Sotirov, 2023). However, this deforestation-free regulation is neither the only instrument, nor the first with similar objectives. Some efforts in the past aiming to curb deforestation and food-system related impacts have relied on market-based mechanisms such as voluntary sustainability standards or third-party certification (Meemken et al., 2021) (albeit with mixed effectiveness due to issues of additionality and leakage (Börner et al., 2020; Dietz & Grabs, 2022)). Other market-related tools have included moratoria and zero-deforestation commitments (Garrett et al., 2019; Gibbs et al., 2015), as well as offsetting or crediting schemes, which have been implemented for carbon in the past and are now garnering momentum for biodiversity (notwithstanding mixed evidence about the effectiveness of these tools as well) (**Figure 4**) (Bidaud et al., 2017; Börner et al., 2017; Droste et al., 2022; Zadek & Herr, 2023). Past efforts have also included non-market and policy instruments at a global-level. This includes internationally agreed-upon biodiversity conservation goals which have outlined objectives for mitigating biodiversity impacts from agricultural trade and global food-systems, e.g., the past Aichi goals and the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. Added to existing free-trade agreements and environmental provisions in existing free-trade agreements (Brandi et al., 2020; UNEP, 2021), it is difficult to distinguish whether this complex constellation of trade-related policies and voluntary efforts fully complement or counter each other.

Nonetheless, given the mixed evidence of effectiveness of past efforts, it seems there is an increasing shift toward more regulatory approaches such as the EU's deforestation-free regulation (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; UNEP, 2021). However, these kinds of regulations have also raised major concerns across countries and sectors, as deforestation-linked agricultural exports may simply shift to other markets such as China, Russia, or the Middle East (i.e., leakage effects), and there would consequently be little-to-no impact in mitigating biodiversity declines. Another concern raised is that the burden of implementing and complying with these measures may fall mostly on less-economically-agile smallholder producers or poorer consumers (Reis et al., 2021).

Figure 4. Summary of governance-related mechanisms via which trade can impact biodiversity.

Traditionally, trade is expected to have negative environmental externalities only when market failures (due to poor governance) prevent any gains in efficiency (see also 1.1). Relatedly, we find mixed expectations regarding the influence of livelihood dependence on export agriculture (which is likely mediated by governance), as this may either increase or decrease pressure on forests and consequently biodiversity. Moreover, governance levels may be expected to have a U-shaped effect on biodiversity, as direct exploitation requires medium governance levels to function, yet is expected to decrease at higher levels with increasing environmental regulations. Finally, we also find a range of mixed expectations regarding the effects of commonly applied market and regulatory instruments for the governance of forests and biodiversity.

With these concerns and governance responses in mind, several research priorities emerge. First, and most broadly, it is important to continue improving our understanding of the underlying governance drivers of environmental impacts in order to fully understand the role of trade in mediating these impacts. Second, it is clear that assessing leakage effects across different market-based and regulatory instruments will be an important factor in ensuring the effectiveness of diverse policies. In this regard, understanding the stickiness of trade relations will likely be a key leverage point, as “stickier” trade relations are expected to be more at risk to source from unsustainable agricultural and forestry practices – yet, these traders may also become change agents as they are less likely to shift sourcing locations in response to new value-chain governance measures. Another leakage aspect to consider is the interaction between export trade and domestic consumption – and whether international export policies are simply shifting domestic sourcing to higher deforestation-risk locations (which can have substantial impact given the high proportions of domestically-produced agriculture) (Pendrell et al., 2022). Third, analyses must better incorporate all actors with transformative potential in agricultural value chains – trading companies, producers, and consumers alike – to better understand who will bear the brunt of compliance across regions and sectors.

Finally, as argued by many studies (Baylis et al., 2021; Kastner, 2021; Lenzen et al., 2012; Ortiz et al., 2021), coherently aligning policies across sectors to address context-

dependent mechanisms that drive biodiversity impacts will be instrumental. It is important to note that policy recommendations across academic disciplines do not necessarily argue for either increasing trade liberalization nor protectionism. Instead, the literature helps identify “lose-lose” scenarios where agricultural production is neither feeding a growing population nor being sustainably produced. In identifying leverage points for the transformation of these systems, it will be important to better understand which proposed tools and mechanisms may also catalyze broader changes in territorial governance.

2. Addressing trade-driven biodiversity impacts

2.1 Current biodiversity metrics

In the past decade, there has been an exponential increase in the number of datasets and indices developed to map global biodiversity patterns. In part, this has been a response to priorities identified by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (Jones et al., 2011), but increasingly also to respond to international policies (IEEP et al., 2021) and the emerging biodiversity offsetting/crediting market which will require these measures to operate (Marshall et al., 2020). Therefore, identifying the most appropriate biodiversity metrics for diverse purposes is essential because failing to do so can be a source of policy ineffectiveness, as well as corporate greenwashing (Koh et al., 2019).

Here, we provide a non-exhaustive overview of currently available biodiversity datasets, and developed metrics and indices (**Table 1**), with the caveat that this is a rapidly developing and dynamic field, and further dataset availability may develop in the near future. Moreover, this landscape may rapidly change with ongoing EU-level efforts aim to establish a standardized approach to biodiversity measurement and valuation (e.g., the EU Business and Biodiversity Platform, or the Align project), alongside business-oriented initiatives such as the Science Based Targets Network, or the Taskforce for Nature-Related Financial Disclosures. Therefore, these metrics cover a variety of dimensions of biodiversity such as the level of ecosystem “integrity”, species monitored populations, species threats and their likelihood of extinction, and their available habitats. Dimensions that are yet to be developed and made available in a similar format as such global datasets are genetic and functional diversity.

Like many other globally modeled data, biodiversity models are based on imperfect and biased samples (Oliveira et al., 2016). As gaps in the global south are particularly pronounced, biases in these data should be taken into consideration when making inferences. As demonstrated by many studies focusing on the LU-related drivers of biodiversity impacts (such as trade-induced LUC), using land or area-based metrics can be a good starting point for evaluating impacts because this directly relates to the main mechanism of biodiversity decline - habitat loss. However, it is important to consider that area-based land metrics alone can misrepresent the effects of agricultural production of particular crops, such as soybeans or palm oil, which are grown on relatively small global areas yet have large biodiversity impacts (Kastner, 2021). Moreover, relying solely on area or land-based metrics can overlook the impacts of land intensification which may affect different taxa (e.g., insects or birds) more than others (e.g., plants) (Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2021). On the other hand, it is also important to note that certain diversity metrics, such as species richness (count of the number of species), are likely to be 1) less sensitive to changes in the landscape such as fragmentation compared to other metrics such as endemism (at least on short time-horizons), and 2) more sensitive to completely new introductions of species (alien, or non-native species), or complete extinctions (which is rarer, though becoming more common (Díaz & Malhi, 2022; Marques et al., 2019)). Hence, using a combination of

land/area-based metrics with other measures of species diversity and distributions, such as richness, abundance (estimates of species' populations), and endemism may provide a more accurate portrayal of biodiversity patterns. Finally, it is key to take into account the spatial and temporal scale at which biodiversity data has been collected, modeled, and analyzed in order to avoid misidentifying or misinterpreting biodiversity patterns at different scales (Gonzalez et al., 2023).

Table 1. Currently available biodiversity metrics or indices developed by a variety of academic, non-governmental, and corporate sources. Adapted and updated from (IIEP et al., 2021).

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Biodiversity Habitat Index (BHI) (v2)	(Harwood et al., 2022) Available at: https://doi.org/10.25919/3j75-f539	Global (30arc-second)	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, and 2020	<p>The BHI estimates the level of species diversity expected to be retained within any given spatial unit (e.g., a country, a broad ecosystem type, or the globe). It is estimated as a function of the unit's area, connectivity, and integrity of natural ecosystems by using remote sensing data and macroecological modelling.</p> <p>It can be expressed as the effective amount of habitat remaining within a unit (e.g., with a score of 100 indicating that a country has experienced no habitat loss or degradation, and 0 a complete loss), or as the proportion of habitat that will result in a proportion of species avoiding extinction in the long-term.</p> <p>It can be used as a conservation-prioritization tool by countries, or as a tool to monitor and report past-to-present trends in expected persistence of species diversity.</p>	Index
Ecosystem Integrity Index (EII)	(Hill et al., 2022) (pre-print)	Global (1km ²)	Not applicable	<p>The EII is an index which incorporates measures of ecosystem integrity via three components: structure, composition, and function. These are measured against a natural, "potential" baseline using a scale of 0-1.</p> <p>Can be used by countries or businesses to establish a baseline and monitor progress towards biodiversity goals or targets.</p>	Index

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Species Habitat Index (SHI)	(Jetz et al., 2012) Available at: https://epi.yale.edu/epi-results/2020/component/shi	Global (country-level)	2001-2019	<p>The SHI measures the proportion of suitable habitats for a country's species that remain intact, relative to a baseline of 2001. It can be calculated for a single species, but is also aggregated into a single score, with species weighted according to the proportion of their global range found in a given country. The SHI serves as a proxy for potential species extinctions, and similarly as the BHI, a score of 100 indicates no habitat loss since 2001, and 0 complete habitat loss.</p> <p>It is a part of the Map of Life data infrastructure of Yale University. It can be used to compare progress across countries.</p>	Index
Global Areas of Habitat (AoH)	(Lumbierres et al., 2022) Available at: https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.02v6wwq48	Global (100m)	2019/2020 (based on data from 2005-2018)	<p>Provides a global map of Areas of Habitat (i.e., habitats available to species within their associated ranges) for 5,481 terrestrial mammal and 10,651 terrestrial bird species.</p> <p>These data can be used for creating global baseline-maps of species (potential) richness.</p>	Dataset
Living Planet Index	(Collen et al., 2009) Available at: https://www.livingplanetindex.org/	Global (point records)	1970-2018 (note variation in time-series across populations; most records cover 6-10 years of population data)	<p>A measure that aggregates and summarizes vertebrate species population sizes from 5,230 species in terrestrial, freshwater, and marine habitats. Using the year 1970 as a baseline, it indicates overall trends of species abundance. It is also possible to subset for only farmland-specialist species.</p> <p>The LPI can be used to understand trends in species populations and the method has been used to produce national-level indices.</p>	Index

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)	(Phillips et al., 2021) Available at: https://www.nhm.ac.uk/our-science/data/biodiversity-indicators/biodiversity-intactness-index-data	Global	Not applicable	<p>The BII is an indicator that measures ecological change in response to human pressures. It is estimated as the percent original number and abundance of species that remains despite these pressures. In other words, it is a composite measure of mean abundance, species richness, and community similarity to that of an “undisturbed” area, measuring the relative “intactness” of nature in different land-use types around the world. It can be averaged across areas, e.g., countries, regions, etc.</p> <p>It uses data from the PREDICTS project (Projecting Responses of Ecological Diversity in Changing Terrestrial Systems), which includes over 54,000 species of birds, mammals, plants, fungi, and insects. Differences in sampling across taxa are statistically accounted for.</p> <p>The BII can be used as an overall indicator for global biodiversity targets, as a baseline to quantify biodiversity losses, as a way to project changes in biodiversity in the future, and as a way to compare the impacts of different crops on biodiversity.</p>	Index

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Human Appropriation of Net-Primary Production (HANPP)	(Haberl et al., 2014; Kastner et al., 2022) Available at: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7313791	Global (5 arc minutes)	1910-2010	<p>HANPP is a measure of the proportion of terrestrial Net Primary Productivity (NPP) that humans consume or “appropriate”. It is measured in units of carbon per year and is the sum of two subcategories: HANPP_{luc} and HANPP_{harv}. HANPP_{harv} is the quantity of carbon in biomass extracted (harvested) by humans or consumed by their livestock per year, including crops, timber, harvested crop residues, forest slash, forages grazed by livestock, and also biomass lost to human-induced fires. HANPP_{luc} denotes alterations in NPP resulting from human-induced land use change, such as the conversion of forest to cropland or infrastructure land. Most recently reconstructed by Kastner et al. (2022).</p> <p>HANPP and its components can also be expressed as the annual percentage of the potential NPP.</p> <p>It can be used as an indicator of human impacts on nature over time.</p>	Dataset
Global Biodiversity Score	(Berger et al., 2021)	Not applicable	Not Applicable	<p>A tool developed to estimate corporate biodiversity footprints. It was developed in cooperation with businesses and financial institutions as well as academics, NGOs and others. It assesses impacts of economic activities across their supply chain, and ecosystem intactness is expressed in a 0-100% scale using the unit of mean species abundance per km² (MSAkm²).</p>	Method/metric proposal and (paid) subscription software
Biodiversity Impact Metric	(University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (CISL), 2020)	Not applicable	Not applicable	<p>A tool developed for corporate businesses to evaluate the level of risk in their agricultural-related supply chains. It is based on three factors, 1) the land area (how many hectares are under production?), 2) quantity impacted (what proportion of biodiversity has been lost through production?), and 3) biodiversity importance (what is the relative global importance of the biodiversity in a particular area?). These three factors are multiplied, which yield a measure of “weighted hectares” impacted by biodiversity.</p>	Method for a metric

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
A practical approach to measuring the biodiversity impacts of land conversion	(Durán et al., 2020)	Not applicable (adaptable to multiple scales as it relates to land-use data)	Not applicable (adaptable to multiple scales as it relates to land-use data)	<p>A methodological framework based on publicly available data that relates specific land-use changes to species-specific habitats and the likelihood of their populations' persistence. Importantly, it allows for incorporating cumulative, nonlinear impacts on species' persistence (i.e. including historical land-use changes) by considering proportional habitat loss compared to species-specific AOH baselines. It may still omit effects on species from habitat fragmentation.</p> <p>Can be used to quantify impacts of human drivers on biodiversity.</p>	Method for a metric
Species Threat Abatement and Restoration (STAR) metric and the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT)	<p>(<i>Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT)</i>, n.d.)</p> <p>Available at: https://www.ibat-alliance.org/simple-downloads?tab=gis-downloads&anchor_id=resource-header</p>	Global (50 km or 5km res)	Not applicable	<p>A metric that quantifies the contributions from mitigating or “abating” threats and restoring habitats in specific places towards reducing species extinction risk. It is derived from the IUCN’s (International Union for Conservation of Nature) Red List, species’ Areas of Habitat, and land cover maps (using a backcasting to model pre-human-impact habitats and land cover to establish a baseline).</p> <p>The STAR score varies from 0 (Least Concern) to 100 (Near Threatened), 200 (Vulnerable), 300 (Endangered), and 400 (Critically Endangered). STAR values across species represents the global threat abatement effort needed for all species to become Least Concern.</p> <p>The IBAT tool and software is geared towards businesses to help them identify assess, reduce, and manage biodiversity extinction risk in specific places (e.g., locations where they produce or source products from)</p>	<p>1) Publicly available dataset (at 50km res)</p> <p>2) Paid software subscription that provides data at 5km² res and guidance for planning corporate responsibility</p>

2.2 A conceptual framework for finding and evaluating trade-linked leverage points to mitigate biodiversity loss

Here, we adapt and expand the framework from the CLEVER project proposal and propose the following conceptual framework, where we demonstrate how the leverage of different interventions on biodiversity outcomes depends on conditions identified in our review:

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for guiding the identification and evaluation of trade-linked leverage points for mitigating biodiversity loss. As we aim to mitigate trade-driven threats to biodiversity, we distinguish between two types of intervention points in the system, those stemming from the production side (*on the left*) (e.g. national environmental and agricultural policies), and those from the consumption side (*on the right*) (e.g., instruments ranging from national policies, to voluntary certification schemes, to due diligence policies, as well as taxes). The leverage that these interventions may have (*illustrated as triangles of potentially different sizes*) depends on a series of conditions identified in the literature. These conditions can range from quality of governance, to inherent conditions that determine the comparative advantage of different locations, to the stickiness of trade relations. Taking these conditions into account will be essential in ensuring the effectiveness of different planned interventions

For instance, the European deforestation regulation is an intervention point where, from the consumption side, the EU must represent a large share of the consumption of the commodities that most highly impact biodiversity to effectively leverage biodiversity outcomes. Moreover, on the production side, the EU deforestation regulation can only have leverage if the countries the EU sources from represent a large share of the production market of those commodities that most highly impact biodiversity. Hence, the leverage of this policy is determined by conditions related to 1) openness to trade

and existing trade agreements, 2) types of crops or commodities produced, and 3) the location of their production in relation to a reference ecosystem.

In another instance, commitments from the private sector (e.g., voluntary certification schemes or zero-deforestation commitments (ZDC's)) can only have leverage on biodiversity outcomes if a sufficient share of actors from the production side make a commitment to more sustainable practices (and similarly to before, if these practices involve commodities that most highly impact biodiversity). In this context, it is evident that the stickiness of trade relations is key in determining the leverage of these commitments on biodiversity outcomes. Highly “sticky” trade relations – where the relationship between producers and buyers is likely to persist regardless of changing conditions – likely have larger potential leverage to change overall production practices, rather than less-sticky trade relations where sourcing may simply shift to other locations.

As a final example, Brazil’s forest code is a national-level policy which aims to regulate deforestation, requiring landowners to maintain a certain percent of land as native vegetation (the percentage which varies across biomes). Hence, the forest code requires sufficient governance capacities to 1) determine an appropriate level of environmental stringency across different biomes and 2) conduct monitoring and enforcement of the policy. Leverage on biodiversity outcomes is also contingent upon the biodiversity-relevance of those areas that are effectively maintained.

CONCLUSIONS

In this review, we have provided an interdisciplinary overview on the expected impacts of agricultural trade on biodiversity outcomes, including the reasons for positive/negative expected effects across different regions and periods, as well as potential governance solutions for the issue. We found that, while the impacts of trade on different aspects of global environmental change (GHG emissions, water and land footprints) have been quantified by a number of different studies, there has been less research specifically focused on biodiversity. Most studies have typically used proxies (e.g. land-use change or forest cover); however, several studies have increasingly begun measuring impacts of trade on species threats (Lenzen et al., 2012) as well as overall declines in biodiversity (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019; Green et al., 2019; Marques et al., 2019). More specific focus on the different dimensions of biodiversity (e.g., genetic or functional diversity) remain under-researched and urgently needed.

We also overviewed how different methods and metrics provide different estimates of the impacts of agricultural trade on biodiversity. On the one hand, different methodological approaches can determine whether studies find net-positive/negative effects. For instance, we show how establishing different temporal or conceptual baselines can determine whether studies find net-positive or net-negative impacts of trade. Studies found net-positive effects from land sparing when comparing to a no-trade scenario (Kastner, 2021), yet other studies found net-negative effects when comparing current impacts to those in the 1980's, or when comparing to future scenarios where agricultural croplands were to be restored to natural vegetation (Marques et al., 2019; Roux et al., 2021). We found that system boundaries of the studies also determined whether net-positive or -negative impacts were found. For instance, if impacts were estimated considering solely ecological or land-use implications they tend to be negative, but if they also factor in socioeconomic implications (e.g., scale, composition, and technique effects of trade, or spillover and leakage effects), these impacts may be neutral or positive (Esty, 2001; Kastner, 2021; Ortiz et al., 2021). On the other hand, differences in findings may also be due to empirical modeling choices, as well as the measurement biodiversity itself – which can include many different dimensions as well (Buschke et al., 2021; Díaz & Malhi, 2022; Gonzalez et al., 2023; Marques et al., 2019).

In sum, current understanding of the overall impacts of agricultural trade on biodiversity does indicate that there is land sparing occurring at global scales, which implies gains in biodiversity conservation. Yet, research also indicates that there are substantial agricultural trade-driven biodiversity declines at local scales. This apparent paradox of different effects at different scales reflects biophysically-determined and historically-grown heterogeneities in the distribution of biodiversity and extant trade relationships. Given these nuanced findings, there are many gaps where further research may help identify points of action for future sustainability efforts.

First, the **measurement of biodiversity** remains an important research gap, and next steps could include specifically testing the implications of different land-use conversions on the diversity and persistence of species and ecosystems (e.g., testing for not only forest loss, but also savannas, shrublands, grasslands, and other LUCs). Better understanding issues in **supply chain transparency** and **determinants of governance effectiveness** also remains an important research gap. Filling this gap can include investigating inter-and-intra regional drivers of policy choice, design, and impact, as well as inter-and-intra regional leakage of such policies and regulations. The stickiness of trade relations as an important factor for both the choice and leakage of policies will also be key to consider. Additionally, it is crucial to consider all actors along supply chains (trading companies, producers, consumers) to understand who has transformative potential, and who will bear the burden of compliance to such policies, as the safeguarding of poor or smallholder producers and consumers alike remains a priority. **Empirical approaches** may include better disentangling agricultural trade-related direct and indirect drivers of biodiversity impacts, as well as identifying and mapping global regions with (un)sustainable comparative advantage (i.e., locations where trade results in an (in)efficient use of resources for the production of agricultural goods). Better understanding the drivers for this inefficiency is key. Better identifying, defining, and testing these drivers – which can often be difficult or ambiguous to identify because they are related to governance issues – remains a priority for finding true leverage points for biodiversity. **Modeling and simulation approaches** in the future may include more actionable counterfactuals than current “no-trade” scenarios (e.g., restoration potential of agricultural lands, reduction in consumption).

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This literature review deliverable contributes towards interdisciplinary approaches to biodiversity research around non-food biomass value chains for the design of more coherent environmental policies. We provide knowledge to better understand the trade-driven impacts on biodiversity, as well as co-benefits and SDG interrelationships. The mapping of mechanisms and identification of research gaps contributes towards the identification of new leverage points.

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